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Resonances from Japan in Modern Danish Architecture. New Evidence from Selected Post-war Domestic Buildings.

Abstract

Although different studies address and evidence the Japanese contributions to Western architecture, there is still limited knowledge and research done about what East Asia meant for modern Danish and Northern European architecture. The internationally renowned post-war Danish buildings built in mid twentieth century, left a leading legacy that has greatly influenced the domestic sphere and has further led the world in terms of good design and welfare. Relevant researchers have pointed out a remarkable and even controversial formal and conceptual connection between traditional Japanese Architecture and some of the most outstanding domestic buildings that marked this age, where there is a special dialogue with Nature. But they present it in general terms, lacking a deep and complete architectural analysis of how this link is achieved.

This study presents the first detailed examination of how this fascinating relationship took place in some outstanding case-studies in Denmark and through what means. It analyses architectural key parameters from different optical lenses and design scales framing relations with the surrounding nature, to evidence the influence and transformative effect of particular traditional Japanese buildings on them. In other words, it determines how the so-called "European Japonisme" translated into these architectural Danish landmarks, what has never been the subject of an integrated comprehensive study.

The findings enrich and transform our understanding of modern Danish architecture, and make an important contribution to our comprehension of the impact that traditional Japanese architecture had on Nordic countries' modern architecture, to activate the cross-cultural exchange between both cultures.

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